

The Influence of Self-Directed Learning on the Overall Learning Abilities of Student

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Abstract:

Learning is a continuous process which involves students' overall development, which comprise knowledge and skills. In the process of academic learning, students take an active participation satisfying the academic standards by encouraging and involving them in the classroom teaching and learning, where teachers play a primary role in acquiring knowledge. Though students were gaining knowledge but were lacking in gaining the skills. Self-Directed Learning (SDL) improves the student's general learning skills by enabling them to involve and develop other skills which include time management, self-assessment and goal setting skills. Self-Directed Learning (SDL) is a method where student involves themselves by taking the initiative of learning, which differs from student to student taking a new direction. Thus, involving themselves individually encourages students to develop hard and soft skills, which is a fundamental requirement for the students in the 21st century.

Keywords: Academic Learning – Self-Directed Learning – Time Management – Goal Setting

Introduction

Learning is a continuous process where students involve voluntarily with an intention to extend the knowledge under the right supervision of the facilitator for correct directions. It involves the students to enable them to cultivate the skill of how to learn, leading to critical thinking. Self-Directed Learning helps the students with better learning ability, where they enjoy the learning with required inputs. Self-directed learning makes students to improve the other skills which include Managerial Skills, Self- Assessment Skills, Time Management Skills and Goal Setting Skills. In other words, students have a clear picture about their learning outcome which they need to compete with the outside world, which becomes be an added advantage for the students to achieve higher self-esteem person with the confidence they work on, as they have clarity about which they are working. By involving in Self-directed Learning students are held responsible for their own learning and the methodology involved in acquiring the knowledge. In this process, students are encouraged in acquiring new information apart from academic knowledge apart from classroom learning which encourages them to compete with the outside world. Student by involving themselves gains the practical exposure which is an advantage to adjust to the workplace environment, where gains knowledge through experience. Students gain the opportunity of refining the existing information which they have on hand.

Self-Directed Learning shifts the paradigm from teacher-centric to student centric, where they can bridge the gap between the past and present information they acquire, laying a strong foundation of their own learning. As students involve voluntarily, they build confidence while developing problem-solving techniques whenever they work on any projects successfully.

Why to develop Self-Directed Learning?

Self-directed learning gives the liberty for the learner to own the responsibility to learn and master the skills. It makes the students' to involve in self-sufficient learning by providing freedom to learn and acquire new or challenging tasks in a unique approach. Students are encouraged to manage the deadlines within the time frame.

Self-Directed Learning makes directs students to involve personally with the enthusiasm and interest, which doesn't happen in training sessions. Student can utilize his own liberty by moving interest in their own phase and limitations and thereby applying their own learning outcomes in different environments which helps them to experience the odd and even situations by laying a platform for improvising.

Benefits of Self-Directed Learning

- Involves students
- Can learn at one's own pace
- Involves Collaborative Learning
- Improves Self-Confidence
- Improves Critical Thinking Skills
- Time Management Skills
- Based on the given tasks students can prioritize the situations
- Students sets for specific goals
- Encourages students for life-long learning
- Enjoys learning
- Improves students Hard Skills and Soft Skills
- Experiences the Life Skills by solving real time problems

Features of Self-Directed Learning (SDL)

- ✓ Self-paced learning
- ✓ Self-involvement
- ✓ Self-motivation

- ✓ Active Learning
- ✓ Sets learning goals
- ✓ Solutions to the problem
- ✓ Evaluates learning
- ✓ Continuous Feedback

Conclusion

In the process of curriculum changes, students need to adopt various situations beyond academic standards to meet the industry's needs. Self-directed learning (SDL) is an explicit approach taken by students, which provides them with the opportunity to develop skills throughout their learning journey. SDL is the basis of all learning domains, which enhances the ability of students to transform their knowledge into learning experiences, leading to significant transformational ideas. The concepts gained through SDL, based on principles, lead to nurturing various skills that continue throughout lifelong learning. Self-involvement by learners using the available resources will harness the skills of the students, leading to effective SDL. The development of both hard and soft skills necessary for the 21st century is achieved through self-directed learning that involves individuals.

References

- 1) Abdullah, M. H. (2001, December). Self-directed learning, Eric Digest, EDO-CS-01-10. Available from: <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED459458.pdf>
- 2) Boud, D (ed) 1988 Developing Student Autonomy in Learning. Kogan Page Limited, London, UK
- 3) Briggs, S. (2015, May 3). Twenty Steps Toward More Self-Directed Learning. Retrieved from <https://www.opencolleges.edu.au/informed/features/29-steps-toward-more-self-directed-learning/>
- 4) Brockett, R G, Hiemstra, R 1991 Self-direction in Learning: Perspectives in Theory, Research, and Practice. Routledge, London, UK
- 5) Brookfield, S D 1986 Understanding and Facilitating Adult Learning. Jossey-Bass Publishers, San Francisco, California
- 6) Caffarella, R S, O'Donnell, J M 1987 Self-directed adult learning: A critical paradigm revisited. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 37: 199-211.
- 7) Candy, P. C. (1991). Self-direction for lifelong learning: A comprehensive guide to theory and practice. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- 8) Davis, L. (2018, April 20). Heutagogy Explained: Self-Determined Learning in Education. Retrieved from <https://www.schoology.com/blog/heutagogy-explained-self-determined-learning-education>.
- 9) Fisher, M., King, J., & Tague, G. (2001). Development of a self-directed learning readiness scale for nursing education. *Nurse Education Today*, 21, 516–525. doi:10.1054/nedt.2001.0589.
- 10) Francis, H. (2017). The Role of Technology in Self-Directed Learning: A Literature Review. Surrey, England: ACS Center for Inspiring Minds. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/35278698/The_role_of_technology_in_self-directed_learning_A_literature_review.
- 11) Garrison, D. R. (1997). Self-directed learning: Toward a comprehensive model. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 48(1), 18–33
- 12) Grow, G. (2009). Teaching Learners to be Self-Directed. Retrieved from <http://longleaf.net/wp/articles-teaching/teaching-learners-text/>
- 13) Guglielmino, L. M. (1978). Development of the Self-Directed Learning Readiness Scale. (Doctoral dissertation, University of Georgia, 1977). *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 38, 6467A
- 14) Hiemstra, R. (1994). Self-directed learning. In T. Husen & T. N. Postlethwaite (Eds.), *The International Encyclopedia of Education* (second edition), Oxford: Pergamon Press
- 15) Knowles, M S 1975 Self-directed Learning: A Guide for Learners and Teachers. Cambridge Book Co., New York

- 16) Long, H B 1989 Self-directed learning: Emerging theory and practice. In: Long, H B and Associates 1989 Self-directed Learning: Emerging Theory & Practice. Oklahoma Research Center for Continuing Professional and Higher Education, University of Oklahoma, Norman, Oklahoma
- 17) Ravid, G 1987 Self-directed learning in industry. In: Marsick, V J (ed) 1987 Learning in the Workplace. Croom Helm, London, UK
- 18) Long, H B and Associates 1991 Self-directed Learning: Consensus & Conflict. Oklahoma Research Center for Continuing Professional and Higher Education, University of Oklahoma, Norman, Oklahoma
- 19) Sale, D. (2018, November 5). A Pedagogic Framework for Developing Self-Directed Learning. Retrieved from <https://blog.softchalk.com/a-pedagogic-framework-for-developing-self-directed-learning>
- 20) Tholin, J. (2008). Learner Autonomy, Self-Directed Learning and Assessment: Lessons from Swedish Experience. Retrieved from <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:870506/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- 21) Zhoc, K., Chung, T., and King, R. (2018). Emotional intelligence and self-directed learning: Examining their relation and contribution to better student learning outcomes in higher education. British Educational Research Journal, 44(6), 982-1004